

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL EDUCATION IN IMPROVING UZBEK LANGUAGE LITERACY AND SPEECH

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Abstract: *Today's student is required to have the ability to compose a clear, expressive, at the same time, impressive and accurate speech in accordance with the speech and social conditions. According to various speech situations, social communication conditions, and the speaker's main goal, different forms of speech occur, and they have their own characteristics as speech styles. The existence of strict rules for the correct selection of language units and their use in accordance with the requirements of the style - requires sufficient knowledge of the rules of style. In the period of integration of the world nations, the issue of Uzbek language literacy is gaining importance. It is becoming necessary for educational tools to develop in accordance with the demands and needs of today's digital generation.*

Kalit so'zlar: *literacy, speech, digital (electronic) education, distance education, mixed (hybrid) education.*

People have long been interested in the issue of beautiful, meaningful speech. In folklore, there are proverbs and wise sayings such as "A good word is the food of the soul", "Even if you speak playfully, speak thoughtfully", "Eating everything is the work of an animal, saying everything is the work of a fool". The appearance of z indicates that the Uzbek people paid attention to speech culture from the beginning.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "It is well known to all of us that the mother tongue is a strong foundation of the nation's spirituality. As our great enlightened grandfather Abdulla Avloni said, the mirror life of each nation that shows its presence in the world is its national language and literature. In this sense, any country that aims to take a worthy place in the world community must first of all preserve and develop the national language and culture of its people" [1].

The field called "Speech culture" and "Language culture" emerged as a new scientific direction in the 60s of the 20th century. But in the studies of this period, speech culture became more of an ideological-ideological propaganda tool than a linguistic phenomenon [2]. The independent state of Uzbekistan has created all the legal bases for the protection and development of the Uzbek language since the first years of independence. Since independence, the Uzbek language is on the path of unprecedented development, the radical renewal of our society, large-scale reforms are contributing to the enrichment of our language. Recently, according to the accounting books of scientists, the amount of knowledge at the disposal of mankind is doubling every ten years, and this situation also leads to the rapid enrichment of the vocabulary of the language.

In order to create a clear, effective and complete speech, the speaker can achieve his goal only if he pays more attention to the content of the speech, the rationale and effectiveness of the speech. In this regard, it is very important to be aware of the secrets of the art of public speaking. Public speaking teaches how to make a correct and effective speech based on the theoretical knowledge obtained from such subjects as linguistics, philosophy, and logic. The purpose of speaking is to accurately and effectively convey what the speaker intended, event, events to the listener. Therefore, it is important to achieve correctness, fluency and logic of speech. Understanding the importance of the language, the speaker should understand the meanings of the words well and make the speech fluently without

haste.

Source historian and linguist Alibek Rustamov: "Moral deficiency is the main reason for the development of barbarism. Spiritual thirst never disappears in a real person. Therefore, it is necessary to constantly worry about satisfying it", he emphasized [3]. Speech culture is a social phenomenon, which develops in close connection with the development of society, science and technology, cultural and literary life. Literature, art, radio, television, periodical press and education have a special role in the formation and development of speech culture.

Speech is an integral part of human life. It should be correct and beautiful both in written and spoken form. Speech culture is the ability to understand the norms and standards of the literary language [4]. Speech culture or speech etiquette - mastering the standards of oral and written literary language (pronunciation, accent, vocabulary, grammar, stylistic rules), as well as from the figurative means of language to the purpose and content of speech in various communication-intervention conditions. is the skill of appropriate use [5]. Speech culture, if the issue is considered from a linguistic point of view, is, first of all, the correctness of speech. Secondly, it should be methodically smooth and fluent [6]. A good speech should be against vagueness, long sentences, brevity, precision and simplicity should be its measure.

The lexicographer Abu Nasr Farabi (870-950) emphasizes the great importance of lexicology, grammar and logic in speaking correctly, making correct logical conclusions, and creating a meaningful and complete speech.

"Qobusnoma" also contains instructive words about speech etiquette and culture, including: "...learn to speak well and don't make a habit of speaking politely, because whatever you want to say, the language will say it. Say the word in its place, a word that is not said in its place, even if it is a good word, looks bad" [7].

The thinker Yusuf Khos Khajib wrote about the correct choice and use of

words in the work "Kutadgu Bilig" ("Knowledge that Brings Happiness"), a wonderful artistic monument of the Turkic peoples of the 12th century: Bilib so'zlese so'z biligke sanur (If the wise speak, the word will be known)" [8].

Our great scholars such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Abu Abdullah al-Khorazmi, Mahmud Koshghari, Zamakhshari wrote works on language, vocabulary, grammar and logic or expressed opinions related to this topic in their works on other fields. [9].

Abdulla Qadiri, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, Oybek, Gafur Ghulam, Abdulla Qahhor, Otajon Hashim, T.N.Qori Niyoz, S.Ibrohimov, Olim Usman contributed to the formation of literary language standards in the 19th and 20th centuries. and others have contributed[10].

By the beginning of the 20th century, the attitude of our intellectuals towards the Uzbek language in the society is getting worse, even those who consider themselves to be advanced representatives of the nation are not paying attention to their mother tongue, which in turn will have sad consequences in the future. they made speeches in the local press with their alarming articles about the possibility of ending with In particular, one of such enthusiasts, Ashurali Zahiri, wrote about his love for his language and its reform in the article entitled "Mother Tongue" published in "Turkestan Regional Gazette" in 1914 (issue 31) [11].

In fact, communication, which is the process of two or more people conveying information to each other and receiving information from each other, in the Uzbek society, the norms of etiquette, politeness, protecting the heart of the interlocutor, careful use of words, it was carried out taking into account dozens of aspects such as the interlocutor's age, social status, mentality, place and time of communication. Only such a sweet conversation gives aesthetic pleasure to both the listener and the speaker, and determines the level and level of education of the participants of the speech dialogue [12].

Alisher Navoi's works "Muhokamat ul-lug'atayn", "Mahbub ul-qulub",

"Nazm ul-javahir" and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Baburnoma" are beautiful examples of speech in Uzbek. Alisher Navoi glorifying the divinity of speech, he insists that the speech of a person who has this priceless gift should always be beautiful, sweet, eloquent and impressive, first of all, he himself rnak will be[13].

In the works of thinkers such as Ogahi, Kamil Khorazmi, Munis Khorazmi, Mashrab, Makhmur, Gulkhani, Nadira, Uvaisi, Muqimi, Furqat, Avaz O'tar oglu, Fitrat, Behbudi, Sufizoda, Hamza, who created in the following centuries, The norms of the classic Zbek literary language were practically perfected, and their works became an invaluable contribution to the development of speech culture.

As the well-known scientist Nazrullo Jorayev rightly wrote in his book "If you are aware...", "Civilization took place in different regions of the world, and the people of certain regions were deeply rooted in their outlook and lifestyle. Civilization, including sophistication in Greece, religion in India, development of material technology in Europe, and morality in Turan" [14]. In our country, morality has been honored as a concept that has no comparison. Qualities such as the ability to speak meaningfully and gracefully, to distinguish between appropriate and inappropriate words in speech, to distinguish the appropriate place, and the manners of speech are among the main pillars of the moral integrity of a person's general morality in Turan.

In particular, in the mother tongue school textbooks, depending on the age of the students, there are topics aimed at the skills of making an effective speech - cultural speech, that is, getting to know the culture of speech, mastering its main concepts.

In the course of the lesson, students are taught a number of communicative qualities such as correctness, accuracy, logicity, expressiveness, richness, purity, expressiveness, which ensure the culture of speech, that is, the power of influence, through explanation and practice. we think that it is one of the urgent tasks of today to create a cultural speech that incorporates all these communicative

qualities in the students' speech.

Regarding the example of a teacher to his students and others, in today's education system, it is a bit more difficult for conscious discipline to take the place of forced obedience in the relationship between teacher and student. The main task of teachers is to develop the skills of independent thinking in students, because if the young generation does not learn to think freely, it is inevitable that the effectiveness of the given education will be low. Therefore, "Knowledge is necessary, but knowledge goes its own way, independent thinking is also a great wealth" [15]. At the same time, all academic subjects in the school, without any exception, should also indirectly deal with the education of speech culture. It is appropriate for the teacher to set an example with his speech culture. In educational practice, teaching speech culture, cultivating the pleasure of beautiful words, and in general, the main, living visual tool in the education of language aesthetics is the teacher himself" [16].

It should not be forgotten that any speech must first of all be correct. But a speech that has only the quality of correctness and is completely devoid of other qualities cannot be considered cultural. At the same time, it is impossible to imagine other communicative qualities that ensure the culture of speech without this quality of correctness. That is why correctness is the primary, first stage of speech culture. Of course, without the main features of this quality, it is impossible to form the skills and abilities of students to make a correct speech. The quality of correctness arises on the basis of full compliance of the structure and construction of the speech with the norms of the current literary language. A speech made without following the standards of literary language cannot be a correct speech. We all know that the literary norm is the rules of using the elements of the language in accordance with the laws of the language, in accordance with the socio-speech practice and tradition stabilized in a certain period of the development of the society, and the following norms are

distinguished in the Uzbek literary language:

- 1) *lexical (word usage) norms;*
- 2) *pronunciation standards;*
- 3) *rules of word formation;*
- 4) *morphological standards;*
- 5) *syntactic norms;*
- 6) *methodological standards.*

Violation of literary language standards in normal speech leads to incorrect structure of speech. There is no doubt that sufficiently understanding each of the speech qualities and being able to express them in speech are aspects that form the basis of a true mastery of cultural speech and the speech perfection of a person. To be able to use the language freely, in accordance with the purpose and the speech situation, the skills, competences and knowledge that ensure the ability to embody all the communicative qualities in the speech require mastering the language with special zeal and diligence. Since language is considered a tool of mental, spiritual and practical aspects of human activity, it can be evaluated as a driving force. This activity is a provider of information exchange between people, ancestors and descendants. In order to preserve and develop it, it is necessary to always think about the protection of the state language.

Today, speech culture is considered a serious scientific field, and the main task of the representatives of this language is to study the existing problems of speech culture, to apply it to practical life, and to attach importance to its integration with all fields. Importance of both types of speech: written and oral speech, the feeling of belonging, leads to the preservation of all features of speech culture. Since speech culture is introduced into the educational and pedagogical process as an educational phenomenon in Uzbek linguistics, it is necessary to create more textbooks and manuals related to this field, to give a wider place in native language curricula and textbooks, and to define speech culture. We think

that it is permissible to organize scientific conferences that justify the content, goals and tasks of the Institute, and to promote and introduce the work done to the general public. It is also important to be able to implement the theoretical points of view in written textbooks and manuals, to convincingly determine the strict dimensions and conditions, peculiarities and limits of cultural speech. In particular, there should be a greater approach to the relationship between speech culture and the art of speaking, expressive reading, aesthetics, ethics, and spelling. The development of scales and criteria for evaluating oral and written skills in order to determine and evaluate students' speaking skills and skills is the basis for improving the education of Uzbek speech culture and improving it.

Great opportunities have been created to increase the importance of the Uzbek language, which is the state language of Uzbekistan, and to apply its norms in all spheres of social life. The implementation of the "Concept of Uzbek language development and improvement of language policy in 2020-2030"[17] is being consistently promoted in all aspects. In this regard, the Department of State Language Development is functioning as the organization responsible for the reforms being implemented [18]. Among a number of tasks of this responsible organization, the development of norms and rules of the written text of the Uzbek language and the acceleration of the work on the full introduction of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script occupy an important place. As a clear evidence of reforms in the field, today the official website of the State Language Development Department (<http://til.gov.uz/>) and <http://matn.uz>, <http://diktant.uz> and <http://tezyoz.uz> websites are operating. These sites are important for today's digital age.

matn.uz and its mobile application were created as a modern form of promotion of mistake writing in Uzbek. This application was developed together with the Project Managers company and the Public Fund for the Support and Development of the National Mass Media, and the use of the site's mobile

application, matn.uz website and special API services for developers is absolutely free[19].

diktant.uz project is an educational campaign aimed at widely promoting the culture of written literacy among the population, especially among young people, increasing respect and interest in the Uzbek language, strengthening its social status, and improving the education of the Uzbek language. [20]. In this campaign, all those who know how to write in Uzbek will have the opportunity to test their knowledge of spelling by taking dictation. In our opinion, the unlimited age of participation in actions organized by the project and aimed at increasing written literacy in the Uzbek language is an important aspect of this educational project.

tezyoz.uz project[21] was established within the framework of the five initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and this educational campaign aims to teach how to write quickly in Uzbek without spelling mistakes and to increase literacy. A notable achievement of the project organizers is the creation of the "offline version download" function to use the site's capabilities without an Internet connection.

In our opinion, it is important to use the materials of the above-mentioned educational sites in the classes of general education institutions and for students to participate in educational campaigns organized on Uzbek language literacy during the academic year. encouragement is appropriate. The processes occurring in the social, political and economic life of the world community will inevitably lead to changes in the field of education. Such trends of the 21st century, continuity and the concept of continuous development allow to implement a number of fundamental reforms in the field of education (distance education, mixed education).

The President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, at the ceremony dedicated to the 30th anniversary of the granting of the status of the state language

to the Uzbek language, said, "...We always support the great interest and aspirations of our young people to learn world languages. Today, I would like to address our dear children and remind them of the wise words of Ishaq Khan Ibrat, a great scholar, who compiled a dictionary in six languages - Uzbek, Arabic, Persian, Hindi, Turkish and Russian at the beginning of the 20th century: "Our youth, of course, let them try to learn another language, but first let them show respect to their mother tongue. After all, loyalty to one's own language is a patriotic duty," he said [22].

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